

Traversing Out-of-Field Teaching: On-hand Experiences of Junior High School Teachers

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Abstract. This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of ten junior high school teachers in public secondary schools in Nabunturan East District, Division of Davao de Oro, as they navigated the complexities of out-of-field teaching assignments. Utilizing in-depth interviews and thematic content analysis, the research uncovered three overarching themes: on-hand instructional and emotional challenges, coping mechanisms for professional adjustment, and insights gained from navigating subject-area mismatches. Despite encountering systemic issues such as limited subject-specific training, inadequate resources, and increased instructional demands, participants demonstrated resilience through self-directed learning, peer collaboration, and a strong professional commitment. Teachers emphasized that flexibility, peer support, and passion for teaching were crucial in overcoming the anxieties of teaching outside their specialization. The study further revealed how institutional support, mentoring, and reflective practices contributed to improved instructional adaptability and professional identity development. These findings accentuated the critical importance of responsive school leadership, targeted professional development, and policies. This study advocates for systemic reforms that support teacher growth, promote equitable subject-area alignment, and foster a culture of resilience and continuous learning within public educational institutions.

KEY WORDS

1. Out-of-field teaching 2. professional resilience 3. self-directed learning

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1. Introduction

Teaching different subjects and grade levels with inadequate training and qualifications, also known as out-of-field teaching, inflicts a substantial burden on educators, requiring them to juggle diverse curriculum demands, instructional strategies, and student needs to different degrees. The responsibility to fit lessons to meet the diverse learning needs of each grade level is a complicated task, often leading to an overwhelming workload for teachers. Balancing the teaching-learning processes for each subject and grade level that suits learners' necessities, places an additional strain on teachers, requiring them to invest considerable time and effort beyond regular working hours. It is then that the burden of out-of-field teaching extends to the emotional labor of addressing the individual concerns and challenges of learners at different stages of their educational journey (Haidar Fand, 2019). In Australia, many teachers are teaching subjects they are not qualified to teach, as highlighted by the latest Australia Council

for Educational Research. At the lower secondary level, it is revealed that 40 percent of year 7 to 10 learners were taught by out-of-field Mathematics teachers (du Plessis, 2019). In South Africa, a significant challenge is the uneven qualifications and specializations among teachers. Educational institutions often need teachers who can competently teach both language and mathematics, even if they lack formal specialization. This requirement highlights the flexibility expected from educators in the system (Gillies, 2019). In Korea, the problem of out-of-field teaching is worsening, making it difficult for teachers to deliver quality instruction to their learners. Their learners are frequently taught by teachers who are unqualified or have a limited understanding of the subject. According to the statistical analysis, 1,410 secondary teachers across the country are teaching out of field, and this requires prompt action to address the worsening situation (Kwak, 2019). Therefore, out-of-field teaching, which is increasingly regarded to as an important and critical issue that can greatly affect the educational system, has become a common occurrence in many countries. However, internationally, there are differences in the way it is manifested, regarded, and responded to. The out-of-field phenomenon arises because of systemic teacher shortages, unequal distribution of teachers, scheduling issues in schools, and the teacher education system in a number of countries where teachers are trained as specialists and not as generalists, thus, there's not enough teachers that match the subjects taught in schools (Kenny, et. al., 2020). In some countries, schools are essentially constrained by funding according to the ratio between teachers and students, therefore it is not always possible to have the right mix of teachers to cover the full spectrum of classes needed, especially in small schools. Within such constraints, out-of-field teaching can be easily overlooked, as many countries clearly regulate what constitutes a professional teacher. In the majority of countries, secondary school teachers are trained as specialists for two subjects, clearly emphasizing that substantial content knowledge is needed to teach at the secondary level (Porsch Whannell, 2019). In the Philippines, out-of-field teaching is also prevalent. Teachers face challenges and struggles when teaching subjects they do not master. Our country faces teacher shortages today, partly due to the Department of Education's K-12 program. The stated program implemented by the Department of Education is one of the reasons for the worsening of the problem of out-of-field teaching in the country. Teaching a low-skilled topic can have a negative impact on a teacher's teaching-learning delivery, which can impede students' acquisition of learning (Arendain Limpot 2022). Teaching out of field presents a challenge for teachers, even in Mindanao, because it requires them to learn new content, which necessitates not only time and effort during their teaching requirements, but also a profound understanding of learning strategies. This makes out-of-field teaching a problem that needs to be addressed for the professional development of teachers, particularly those who teach non-specialized subjects (Weldon, 2019). The phenomenon of out-of-field teaching, where educators teach subjects for which they lack specialized training or qualifications, presents a significant gap in educational practice. This situation often arises due to staffing shortages, particularly in areas such as STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines or specialized subjects. From this standpoint, the need to conduct a qualitative investigation into navigating out-of-field teaching was recognized. The study aims to explore the firsthand experiences of junior high school teachers in secondary public schools. This exploration is essential for comprehensively understanding the challenges and obstacles faced by educators teaching subjects outside their expertise. Out-of-field teaching can have adverse effects on student learning outcomes, as teachers may lack

the depth of knowledge and pedagogical expertise required to teach these subjects effectively. Addressing this gap is crucial for ensuring that students receive high-quality instruction that aligns with curriculum standards and promotes their academic success. This study will benefit various stakeholders that include policymakers,

educational administrators, teacher training institutions, and ultimately, students themselves. By identifying the extent of out-of-field teaching, understanding its impacts on student learning, and exploring strategies to mitigate this issue, policymakers can develop targeted interventions and allocate resources effectively.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore the out-of-field teaching challenges and opportunities that could bring out the lived experiences of the junior high school teachers. Thus, this research will focus on the direct and immediate experiences of out-of-field junior high school teachers. It is known that out-of-field teaching has received less research. This has been the motivation for this study to be conducted immediately, which will help teachers, especially

the teachers who teach the subject they have not mastered. This study explores the out-of-field teaching from the following perspectives: conceptualizing out-of-field teaching, ongoing teacher learning, and formal professional development. Specifically, the study aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of their on-hand experiences in the out-of-field teaching as drawn from the findings of the study that was conducted in Nabunturan East District, Division of Davao de Oro.

1.2. Research Questions—This study was conducted to explore the challenges and opportunities experienced by junior high school teachers in teaching out-of-field subjects. The direction of the study was guided by the following specific research questions:

- (1) What are the on-hand experiences of the out-of-field teachers?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms on the challenges?
- (3) What are insights and lesson learned that can be drawn from the study?

1.3. Significant of the Study—This study will be beneficial to the Department of Education, school principals, teachers, and learners.

Teachers

Teachers will benefit from this study as it en-

courages a reflective approach to teacher preparation and ongoing professional development, fostering an environment where educators are better equipped to adapt to changing educational settings and diverse classroom situations.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This study is supported by the Person-Environment Fit Theory, also known as P-E Fit theory of Lawton (1985). This theory suggests that individuals seek environments that complement their needs, abilities, and values, and that the level of fit between a person and their environment influences various outcomes such as job satisfaction, performance, and overall life satisfaction. The theory highlights two types of fit: person-job fit and person-organization fit. Person-job fit examines

the compatibility between an individual's skills, knowledge, and abilities and the requirements of a specific job, while person-organization fit considers the alignment between an individual's values and goals with the values and goals of the organization. A high level of person-environment fit is associated with greater well-being, motivation, and performance, while a poor fit may lead to stress, dissatisfaction, and reduced productivity. In essence, the Person-Environment Fit Theory accentuates the vigor-

ous interaction between individuals and their surroundings, emphasizing the importance of a harmonious match for optimal psychological and organizational outcomes. This theory holds significant relevance to out-of-field teaching, where educators find themselves in roles or subjects outside their primary areas of expertise. In such situations, the theory becomes a valuable framework for understanding the compatibility between the teacher and the unfamiliar teaching environment. Out-of-field teachers often face challenges related to their knowledge, skills, and experiences, which may not perfectly align with the demands of the new educational setting. The theory suggests that for effective teaching and positive outcomes, it is crucial to assess and enhance the fit between the teacher and the teaching environment. Schools and educational institutions can use this theory to recognize the specific needs, strengths, and preferences of out-of-field teachers and provide tailored support and professional development opportunities. By addressing the person-environment fit, administrators can foster a more conducive atmosphere for out-of-field educators, potentially improving their job satisfaction, confidence, and overall effectiveness in the classroom. Another theory that was useful in this study is the Lev Vygotsky's Social Constructivist Theory (1934) has had a profound impact on the field of education, shaping our understanding of how learning and cognitive development take place. According to Vygotsky, learning is a social and cultural activity, and individuals actively construct knowledge through interactions with their environment and others. The Social Constructivist Theory proves remarkably useful in the context of out-of-field teaching practices. It also puts emphasis on the social and collaborative nature of learning aligns well with the challenges faced by educators when navigating unfamiliar subject matter. In out-of-field teaching scenarios, where teachers may not possess in-depth expertise in the assigned content,

the theory provides a context to leverage social interaction and collaborative learning. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the opportunities of teachers in out of field teaching; challenges of teachers in out-of-field teaching, and insights drawn from the experiences and challenges of teachers in out of field teaching. The combination of Person-Environment Fit Theory and Vygotsky's Social Constructivist Theory offers a clear view of the experiences of out-of-field teachers. The P-E Fit Theory explains that a mismatch between a teacher's skills and their subject can result in stress, dissatisfaction, and lower effectiveness. Vygotsky's theory shows that these issues can be tackled through social interaction, collaboration, and shared learning. Together, these theories stress the need for schools and policymakers to create supportive environments. Schools can help ease mismatches through mentorship, peer learning, and focused professional development. They also highlight the need for changes in how teachers are placed and trained. Schools should not see out-of-field teaching just as a staffing problem, but as a chance for growth and change. The integration of Person-Environment Fit Theory and Social Constructivist Theory highlights the complex nature of teaching, particularly in out-of-field situations. The P-E Fit Theory focuses on how well a teacher aligns with their work environment, while Vygotsky's theory emphasizes that learning and adaptation occur through collaboration and guided interaction. Out-of-field teachers can bridge skill gaps by working with experienced peers, joining communities of practice, and co-planning lessons, aligning with Vygotsky's concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), where growth happens through scaffolded support. This theoretical combination also offers practical insights for educational leadership and policy. Through the P-E Fit lens, school leaders can assess teacher

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

readiness before assigning out-of-field roles. Meanwhile, Vygotsky’s ideas support the establishment of collaborative practices such as learning action cells (LACs), peer mentoring, and team teaching. These strategies foster a culture of reflection and shared growth, allowing schools to view out-of-field teaching not as a mere staffing issue, but as an opportunity for continuous professional and instructional development. Together, these theories emphasize the importance of intentional support systems for out-of-field teachers. By recognizing both the internal fit between teacher and role, and the external value of collaborative learning, schools can better address the challenges these educators face.

2. Methodology

This chapter described the different parts of the research method. It covered the methods used, the selection of participants, the techniques for collecting data, my role as the researcher, the steps for analyzing data, and the measures taken to ensure the study’s credibility and adherence to ethical standards. Conducting this research required a careful and organized approach. I detailed this in the section to ensure both thoroughness and authenticity. I used two primary qualitative methods: in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). Each method was chosen for its ability to capture specific types of data. In-depth interviews allowed me to gather detailed personal experiences and viewpoints, especially on sensitive topics. Focus group discussions provided insights into group dynamics, shared values, and common concerns among educators. Together, these methods painted a fuller picture of out-of-field teaching in junior high school. Guided by phenomenology, I focused on exploring the experiences of teachers as they faced and understood teaching outside their specialization. This approach, based on Creswell’s (2020) framework, helped me grasp not just what the teachers experienced, but also how they

interpreted those experiences in the larger educational context. By focusing on their perspectives through interviews, observations, and thematic analysis, phenomenology provided a powerful way to uncover deeper meanings and offer thoughtful insights into the complicated realities of out-of-field teaching.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—This study was grounded in philosophical beliefs that informed how I collected, analyzed, and interpreted the data. These core beliefs played a crucial role in guiding the research process and influenced the conclusions I reached. Drawing on Stanage (1987), I understood a paradigm as a model or pattern that serves as a guide for research actions and decisions. Denzin and Lincoln (2000) built on this by defining a research paradigm as a fundamental set of beliefs, a worldview that informs how a researcher engages with their study. These perspectives helped me stay aware of my own role and orientation during the research, making sure my approach was intentional and reflected my philosophical stance.

Ontology

Ontology shaped my understanding of reality as seen by the participants. Following Creswell (2020), I believe that reality is subjective and differs for each person. I noticed that each participant created their version of reality, based on their unique experiences. In this study, I examined the lived experiences of junior high school teachers who taught subjects outside their areas of specialization. My goal was to understand the challenges they faced and the chances for their professional growth. I collected and examined the data to reflect these different viewpoints. I worked to keep the authenticity of their responses while avoiding any personal bias in my interpretations.

Epistemology

In this study, I strongly believed that being close to the participants was essential to gathering authentic and meaningful insights. I didn't want to be a distant observer. Instead, I chose to immerse myself in the environment and build

real connections with the teachers I was learning from. I took time to engage with them, listen to their stories, and understand their experiences from their perspectives. This approach helped me collect data that reflected their true thoughts and feelings. Using a phenomenological design and thematic analysis, I explored the lived experiences of junior high school teachers in the Nabunturan East District who were teaching subjects outside their area of specialization. My goal was not just to gather information. I aimed to truly understand their realities and present them in a way that honors their voices. This deep involvement helped me notice the subtle emotions, challenges, and coping strategies that might have been missed in a more detached approach. It also built trust, encouraging participants to share openly about their struggles and successes. Ultimately, this immersive and empathetic method improved the depth and authenticity of the study's findings.

Axiology

I also recognized the importance of values in the research process. Creswell (2020) pointed out that axiology requires researchers to be open about how their own values might shape their interpretation of data. I was very aware of this throughout my work. I prioritized respecting the personal and value-driven nature of the insights shared by the participants. I understood that their stories held meaning based on their individual experiences. As I analyzed the data, I carefully interpreted their responses with respect and sensitivity. I always aimed to stay true to their perspectives and not let my own biases interfere.

Rhetoric

Staying true to qualitative research, I chose a rhetorical approach that let my participants' voices shine. I shared their stories through nar-

native, aiming to capture the depth and richness of their experiences. As I presented the findings, I used my own voice to tell their journeys, describing their challenges and insights as they navigated out-of-field teaching. I made a deliberate effort to use clear, relatable language and avoided overly technical terms so that a wider audience could understand and connect with

their lived experiences. I also made sure that the participants' views were represented accurately by including direct quotes that showed their feelings and thoughts. This approach let readers hear not only what was said but also how it was expressed, bringing their struggles and growth to life.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology referred to the overall research approach, while method pertained to specific procedures (Gerodias, 2013). To capture the experiences of junior high school teachers, I conducted in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. My goal was not just to collect data; I wanted to explore the meanings behind personal stories. Using a phenomenological design let me focus on the essence of out-of-field teaching. It helped me uncover key themes and insights that might not show up in surface-level observation. I based this study on the belief that human experience is a valid source of knowledge, as Creswell (2020) noted. I also accepted that our everyday realities can offer powerful insights into how people behave, adjust, and understand their world. Through this method, I looked into both the “what” and the “how” of the teachers' experiences, following Moustakas' (1995)

framework. This approach helped me understand the reality faced by out-of-field teachers.

Design and Procedure

In conducting this study, I chose a phenomenological approach because I wanted to understand the teachers' experiences as they saw them. My goal was to uncover the meaning behind their stories without letting my own assumptions interfere. I gathered rich, detailed data through qualitative methods such as interviews and observations, allowing the participants to speak freely about their realities. By setting aside my biases, I focused on the heart of their lived experiences. As Forris (2015) pointed out, phenomenology aims to show reality from the participants' perspective. This approach allowed me to gain a deeper, more personal understanding of what junior high school teachers face when teaching outside their field of expertise.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Throughout the research process, I was diligent in upholding ethical principles. I prioritized integrity in all my actions, making sure the information I gathered, interpreted, and presented was handled honestly and respectfully. I secured informed consent and maintained the confidentiality of my participants. I felt responsible for conducting research that reflects truth and ethical accountability.

cial value because it highlighted the real experiences of junior high school teachers facing the challenges of teaching out of their field. I felt a strong need to show how teacher misassignment affects both the educators and the quality of education they provide. Through this study, I aimed to share helpful insights that educational authorities could use when developing support programs and creating policies that address the needs of classroom teachers. My goal was to ensure this work was meaningful and relevant to those directly affected by these issues.

Social Value

For me, this research held significant so-

Informed Consent

As part of my ethical commitment to this study, I made sure to obtain informed consent from all participants. Following McLeod's (2009) Treaty Principle of Participation, I ensured that each teacher understood their participation was entirely voluntary and based on enough information about the research. I outlined the recruitment process in detail in the study's appendices to maintain transparency. I knew building trust was important for meaningful engagement, as highlighted by Walker (2007, cited in Pillerin, 2012). Before conducting any interviews, I provided participants with consent letters. These letters explained the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and what was expected of them. Only those who re-

viewed, signed, and returned the consent forms took part in the research. I also made it clear that participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences.

Vulnerability of Research Participants

The participants in this study were all professional teachers in public junior high schools, allowing them to answer the research instrument confidently. I made sure they felt supported during the process. I assured them that they could easily reach me through my contact information and address if they had any questions or needed more clarification about the study. This open line of communication helped build trust and ensured they felt comfortable and informed throughout their participation.

2.4. Research Participants—In qualitative research, I understood that smaller sample sizes are often better than those used in quantitative studies, as long as they capture a diverse range of viewpoints related to the topic. I followed the concept of saturation, i Glaser and Strauss in 1967. This concept refers to the point at which no new themes or insights appear, indicating that the sample size is sufficient. For this phenomenological study, I referred to Creswell's recommendation in 2020, which suggests involving between 5 to 25 participants. Instead of relying on a fixed number, I based the sample size on the study's purpose, available resources, and time limits. To select my participants, I used purposive sampling, a non-probability method focused on selecting individuals based on specific traits relevant to the study's goals. This technique, also known as

judgmental or selective sampling, allowed me to choose participants who could provide rich and relevant insights intentionally. I invited 10 public junior high school teachers from Nabunturan East, Davao de Oro, for in-depth interviews with five and a focus group discussion with the remaining five. All participants met the inclusion criteria, being permanent public secondary school teachers with at least three years of teaching experience. Their lived experiences helped me identify meaningful patterns and themes related to out-of-field teaching. Using purposive sampling ensured that the voices included in this study were genuine and closely aligned with the research objectives. It allowed me to gather detailed, experience-based data from those best positioned to reflect on the phenomenon of teaching outside one's area of specialization.

2.5. Role of the Researcher—As the researcher, I played a key role in uncovering, sharing, and using knowledge to help educational institutions. During this study, I took on mul-

iple responsibilities that were essential to the research's integrity and success. These tasks included carefully collecting and interpreting data, engaging meaningfully with participants, and

turning findings into insights that could guide educational practices and policies. My active involvement made sure the study reflected the real experiences of educators and added to the wider academic discussion on out-of-field teaching. I consistently upheld ethical standards to protect the participants' confidentiality and ensure their voices were heard with respect. I also reflected critically on my own biases and assumptions to maintain the credibility of the research. Through this commitment, I contributed not only to scholarly understanding but also to the practical improvement of teacher support systems.

Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research

I interviewed the participants and guided them carefully during the research process. When analyzing their responses, I made sure that my interpretations were based on existing

2.6. Data Collection—I used a clear process to gather data for this study. First, I got an endorsement letter from the Dean and attached it to the letter of request to conduct study, which I submitted to our OIC- Schools Division Superintendent. After I received an approval, I asked permission from the school heads so I can gain access to their school and interview their teachers. After conducting detailed interviews by using a voice recorder and taking down notes, I transcribed the participants' responses with care to capture their true meaning. Next, I familiarized, coded the data, and analyzed the themes, identifying key patterns that reflected the participants' experiences. This methodical approach helped me uncover valuable insights while preserving their authenticity.

Securing Endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School

I got an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges. This letter was needed to request formal

literature and related studies, not on my personal knowledge, beliefs, or feelings. I chose this approach to reduce bias and maintain the objectivity and credibility of the research findings.

Expert in Qualitative Methods

To ensure I implemented the qualitative methodology properly, I continuously assessed myself and sought regular guidance from my research adviser and other professionals. These reflective and consultative practices helped me show I was skilled in conducting interviews according to the research design, making accurate field observations, and choosing relevant artifacts, images, and journal excerpts. I also used Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis effectively. This approach kept the study rigorous and produced credible, meaningful findings.

approval to conduct the study from the Schools Division Superintendent. To ask for permission from the Schools Division Superintendent, I submitted a formal letter along with Chapters 1 and 2 of the study and the research instrument that described the study's goals and intended participants. I made sure all the paperwork was complete and clearly explained the purpose and scope of the research. After that, I waited for the official approval before starting any data collection activities, following all institutional and ethical guidelines.

Coordinating with School Heads

Upon receiving approval from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS), I sent formal letters to the principals of the identified schools to inform them about the purpose and scope of my study. I clearly explained the objectives, significance, and ethical considerations of the research to gain their support and ensure full cooperation throughout the data collection process.

Obtaining Consent from Participants

I ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study through an orientation that explained its purpose, process, risks, and benefits. Informed consent was obtained, emphasizing their rights, including the freedom to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Conducting the Interview

I conducted in-depth interviews using a structured questionnaire designed to elicit rich, meaningful responses aligned with the study's objectives. Prior to each interview, I documented participant profiles to provide context for their insights. During the sessions, I took detailed notes and used audio recordings to ensure the accuracy of subsequent transcriptions. Throughout the interviews, I maintained ac-

tive listening and sustained engagement, creating a respectful and open environment that encouraged participants to share their experiences freely and authentically.

Transcribing the Responses

I transcribed the interviews verbatim using the audio recordings to preserve the accuracy and integrity of the participants' responses. When participants expressed themselves in their native language, I carefully translated their responses into English to ensure consistency in the analysis. This translation process was handled with cultural sensitivity and attention to meaning, so as to maintain the authenticity of their perspectives while enabling coherent thematic interpretation across all data.

2.7. Data Analysis—I employed thematic analysis, guided by Creswell's (2020) model of identifying themes, to analyze the participants' responses systematically. The process began with familiarization, during which I immersed myself in the data by repeatedly reading the interview transcripts and noting initial insights. This step allowed me to gain a deeper understanding of the participants' lived experiences and perspectives. Through this reflective engagement with the data, I laid the groundwork for identifying meaningful codes and generating themes that accurately represented the core essence of the phenomenon under study.

Coding

I generated concise labels or codes for relevant segments of the data, capturing both the literal content and the underlying interpretative meanings. Every data item was systematically coded to ensure comprehensive coverage and consistency. Related excerpts were then collated and grouped according to their respective codes, providing a structured foundation for deeper analysis and the subsequent development of themes. This process allowed me to

maintain analytical rigor while remaining faithful to the participants' authentic voices.

Searching for Themes

I carefully reviewed the coded data to identify coherent patterns and emerging themes that aligned with the research questions. This involved examining the relationships among codes and assessing their relevance to the core objectives of the study. I then grouped related data according to these emerging themes, ensuring that each theme reflected a meaningful and accurate representation of the participants' experiences. This thematic organization provided a clear and structured way to address the research questions and interpret the findings.

Reviewing Themes

I looked closely at the consistency and importance of the identified themes. I wanted to make sure each theme told a meaningful story about the participants' experiences. In refining these themes, I worked to show the depth and complexity of the data in a clear and organized way. Following the approach outlined by King and Brooks (2018), I viewed thematic analysis as a dynamic and interpretive process. I recog-

nized that themes are created actively, not just discovered. In line with their view, I continually refined my work, carefully assessing the clarity and coherence of each theme. I aimed to ensure

2.8. *Framework of Analysis*—I adopted a flexible framework analysis approach for this study, which allowed me to analyze the data either concurrently with or after data collection. This adaptability provided the opportunity to engage deeply with the data while maintaining alignment with the evolving context of the research. I systematically examined and organized the data according to key themes and issues that emerged during the analysis. This process followed the five main steps outlined by Ritchie and Spencer (1994): familiarization with the data, identifying a thematic framework, indexing, charting, and finally, mapping and interpretation. Each step was carried out with rigor to ensure that the findings were analytically sound and reflective of the participants' lived experiences.

Familiarization

I reviewed the interview transcripts and field notes thoroughly and listened attentively to the audio recordings to immerse myself in the data. Through this process of familiarization, I gained a comprehensive understanding of the participants' narratives. As I engaged with the material, I noted key ideas and recurring patterns that began to surface, laying the groundwork for the development of a thematic framework that would guide the subsequent stages of analysis.

Identifying a Thematic Framework

Drawing from the insights and recurring issues that emerged during the familiarization process, I developed a thematic framework to guide the analysis. This framework was shaped by both the study's research objectives and the content shared by the participants. By aligning the themes with the participants' lived experiences and the overarching aims of the research, I en-

that each one accurately represented the participants' stories and fit with the main goals of the study.

sured that the framework provided a structured yet responsive basis for organizing and interpreting the data.

Indexing

I systematically tagged sections of the data according to the relevant themes identified in the thematic framework. This process was applied consistently across the entire data set to ensure thoroughness and coherence. To facilitate organization and ease of reference during analysis, I employed a numerical coding system. This approach allowed me to efficiently retrieve and compare data segments, enhancing the accuracy and depth of the thematic interpretation. Also, this structured process helped maintain analytical transparency and traceability from raw data to emerging insights and themes. Charting

In addition to enhancing analytical clarity, the reorganization of data into a thematic framework served as a critical step in establishing coherence within the study's findings. By visually categorizing the data in charts, I was able to isolate recurring trends and distinct outliers, making it easier to identify the core aspects of the out-of-field teaching experience. This method not only simplified the task of making sense of large volumes of qualitative data but also provided a clearer picture of how specific factors, such as teacher background and teaching context, influenced the experiences of out-of-field educators. The use of charts acted as a visual aid for both myself and future readers of the research, providing an accessible way to navigate complex qualitative material. Furthermore, the thematic framework allowed me to engage more deeply with the data during the analysis process. It prompted me to reflect on how individual teacher experiences could be interpreted within

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

the larger context of educational theory, such as Person-Environment Fit Theory. By aligning the findings with well-defined themes, I was able to draw meaningful connections between the teachers' challenges and the theoretical underpinnings of the study.

Mapping and Interpretation

I examined the organized data carefully to identify emerging patterns, relationships, and key insights that would shape the final interpretation and overall conclusions of the study. This phase marked a transition from description to analysis, requiring me to engage deeply with the data in order to uncover meaning beyond surface-level observations. To support this analytical process, I created both visual and conceptual representations, such as thematic maps, coding matrices, and mind maps, which helped in organizing the data coherently and enhancing my understanding of its underlying structure. These tools provided a framework that made it easier to detect links across cases and to visualize the complex dynamics of out-of-field teaching as described by the participants.

Throughout this process, I was guided by the fundamental goals of qualitative data analysis, as outlined by Ritchie and Spencer (1994:186). These goals include defining key concepts, mapping the range and nature of phenomena, developing classifications, identifying patterns and connections, explaining observed phenomena, and generating strategies that can address real-world concerns. I was intentional in applying these analytical aims to my own study, particularly in maintaining the integrity of the data and ensuring that the final interpretations stayed true to the participants' lived experiences. Each code and category were reviewed multiple times, and constant comparison techniques were applied to refine and validate emerging themes. To make sure that my findings are accurate, I based all concepts and themes on the participants' actual narratives. This allowed their voices to structure the analysis while I remained aware of my personal biases. By paying close attention to both the content and the context, including tone, emphasis, and delivery, I captured the depth and complexity of their experiences.

2.9. Trustworthiness of the Study—

For this qualitative study, I placed great importance on establishing trustworthiness by ensuring credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability throughout the research process. Trustworthiness is essential in evaluating the worth and integrity of a qualitative study, as the results and findings are deeply rooted in how the research is conducted. Given the interpretive and subjective nature of qualitative inquiry, I committed to maintaining honesty,

transparency, and accuracy in all data collection and analysis procedures. By upholding these principles, I aimed to produce findings that are not only valid and meaningful but also reflective of the participants' true experiences. Establishing trustworthiness ensured that the study would be respected within the academic community, worthy of being read, shared, and regarded with confidence.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. On-Hand Experiences of the Out-Of-Field Teaching—Out-of-field teaching exposes educators to unfamiliar territories, requiring them to teach subjects beyond their specialization. These on-hand experiences often involve steep learning curves, as teachers must simultaneously study new content and design effective instruction for students. The lack of formal training in the assigned subject matter challenges their confidence and competence, prompting them to seek alternative teaching strategies. Despite the difficulty, many teachers report that the experience pushes them to become more flexible, resourceful, and innovative in their approach. Moreover, the process often demands significant time for preparation, especially in developing learning materials and mastering subject-specific competencies. Teachers are forced to adapt their pedagogical methods, experiment with interdisciplinary techniques, and draw from peer support or personal interests to bridge knowledge gaps. These real-world experiences, though challenging, foster professional growth and broaden their instructional skills. Ultimately, on-hand experiences in out-of-field teaching serve as both a test and a catalyst for educators' resilience, creativity, and dedication to quality education.

3.1.1. Content and Pedagogical Adjustment—Teachers reported that one of the most

immediate and challenging aspects of out-of-field teaching is the need to adjust both content knowledge and pedagogy. Teaching subjects outside their area of expertise often means acquiring new conceptual understanding and altering their teaching styles accordingly. What works in one subject may not work in another, especially when moving from theoretical to practical or performance-based content. This adjustment requires flexibility, research, and a willingness to fail and improve through trial and error. Another component of pedagogical adjustment involves understanding how students engage with the new subject area. Teachers must tailor strategies that fit the nature of the subject and the learner's needs. Often, this is done with limited resources or guidance, making the learning curve steeper. Nonetheless, most participants demonstrated resilience and adaptability in adjusting to unfamiliar topics and teaching dynamics. The findings of the study support Weldon (2019), who reported that a significant proportion of junior secondary teachers are assigned to teach subjects they did not specialize in, contributing to major instructional challenges. His research revealed that teachers often feel unprepared, and struggle with both confidence and mastery of unfamiliar subject content. Despite this, he observed that many educators gradually develop resourcefulness and

resilience in the face of their new responsibilities. Weldon emphasized that such on-hand experiences are transformative, albeit demanding, often reshaping teachers' professional identity. The results support Kenny (2020), who pointed out that teachers involved in out-of-field teaching often show impressive adaptability. They take charge of their own learning, which leads to ongoing professional growth and resilience. Porsch (2019) highlighted the importance of institutional support, stressing that schools must conduct needs analyses and offer targeted mentoring to help teachers thrive in unfamiliar teaching contexts. Weldon (2019) pointed out that many teachers succeed in out-of-field assignments not merely due to subject knowledge, but because of their deep passion and strong sense of responsibility toward students. (Du Plessis McDonagh, (2021) added that professional development programs must be carefully aligned with teacher motivations and real classroom needs to be effective, particularly for those navigating unfamiliar subject areas.

3.1.2. Emotional Pressure and Performance Anxiety —Out-of-field teaching often brings about emotional strain, especially among teachers who feel inadequate or underprepared. Several respondents described feelings of pressure, anxiety, and even fear that they might not meet expectations or adequately support students' learning. This internal conflict is fueled by the weight of responsibility and the fear of delivering subpar education. It adds emotional labor on top of cognitive and professional challenges. Teachers also mentioned that performance anxiety is intensified when multiple out-of-field subjects are assigned simultaneously. They are required to balance mastery, lesson planning, and classroom engagement across unfamiliar content areas, often without clear direction. These experiences can lead to frustration, low morale, or feelings of being undervalued. Yet, in many cases, the struggle led to self-discovery and improved emotional resilience

over time. Kwak (2019) described the worsening situation of out-of-field teaching in Korea, where more than a thousand secondary teachers are delivering instruction outside their areas of expertise. He stressed that this mismatch often results in poor-quality teaching and reduced student outcomes due to inadequate subject knowledge. Kwak's study also underscored the emotional toll on teachers, who frequently experience anxiety and a lack of confidence. These conditions reflect the urgent need for policy-level interventions to improve the teaching environment.

3.1.3. Innovative and Creative Teaching Techniques —Despite the many difficulties, some teachers embraced out-of-field teaching as a space for creativity and innovation. Respondents highlighted how unfamiliar subjects allowed them to experiment with new strategies, teaching aids, and engagement techniques. This space fostered personal growth and pedagogical innovation, even as teachers worked outside their original training. Teachers often combined their personal interests or prior experiences to make the lessons more relatable and effective. This theme reveals that out-of-field teaching can be an avenue for transformation, not just a compromise. Teachers who take creative risks are able to not only deliver the curriculum but also bring something new and engaging to the classroom. Their strategies include interdisciplinary approaches, integration of arts, and contextual teaching methods. These adjustments not only enrich the learning process but also empower teachers to redefine their professional identities. Du Plessis (2019) emphasized that out-of-field teaching is prevalent in low socioeconomic and rural areas, particularly in Australia, where over 40% of students in certain subjects are taught by out-of-field teachers. His work highlighted that while many educators report being overwhelmed, the experience also fosters professional adaptability and awareness of pedagogical gaps. Du Plessis argued that such ex-

Fig. 3. On-Hand Experiences of the Out-Of-Field Teaching

periences challenge teachers to think creatively, ground realities underscore the complexity and often leading to novel approaches in lesson delivery and content understanding. These on-the- dual nature of out-of-field teaching experiences.

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms on the Challenges of Out-of-Field Teaching*—Out-of-field teaching poses a significant challenge, yet it also serves as a powerful catalyst for growth through self-directed learning and personal initiative. Teachers placed outside their areas of expertise often take the initiative to independently explore content, utilize online resources, and engage in ongoing professional development to bridge knowledge gaps. This proactive stance not only enhances instructional quality but also builds confidence and a sense of autonomy. In this way, personal initiative becomes a core coping strategy that empowers educators to turn challenges into opportunities for professional enrichment. Equally important are collaboration and peer support, alongside a positive mindset and strong professional commitment, in navigating the emotional and instructional de-

mands of out-of-field teaching. By seeking advice, co-planning lessons, and sharing resources with colleagues, teachers develop a supportive network that eases stress and fosters collective problem-solving. Maintaining a positive outlook and a deep sense of responsibility toward student learning motivates teachers to persist, even when faced with subject-area uncertainties. These interconnected themes form a comprehensive coping framework that sustains teacher effectiveness, resilience, and growth in the face of professional adversity. They also highlight the importance of both individuality and institutional support in navigating the complex realities of out-of-field teaching.

3.2.1. *Self-Directed Learning and Personal Initiative* —A significant coping mechanism among out-of-field teachers is self-directed learning. Teachers take the initiative to

study subject matter independently using available resources like textbooks, online platforms, and educational videos. This proactive behavior is driven by a desire to meet academic standards and compensate for the lack of formal training in the assigned subjects. Self-learning not only helps them deliver content more confidently but also reinforces their sense of professional responsibility. This coping strategy also illustrates a high level of teacher agency and ownership over their roles. Instead of waiting for institutional support, these educators take it upon themselves to bridge the knowledge gap. Their commitment to continuous improvement demonstrates resilience and dedication to student outcomes. It also helps them gradually gain mastery in new teaching areas, making future assignments more manageable. Kenny et al. (2020) highlighted that coping with out-of-field teaching begins with self-directed learning and teacher initiative. His findings revealed that many teachers develop coping strategies by independently studying their assigned subjects and engaging with online materials or informal mentorship. Kenny emphasized that such autonomy empowers teachers and enhances their capacity to teach effectively, despite initial setbacks. This proactive approach is seen as a foundational response to the systemic gap created by subject mismatches. Porsch and Whannell (2019) discussed how teachers' coping mechanisms are influenced by both personal attitudes and institutional structures. They observed that schools that recognize and address the nuanced needs of out-of-field teachers help foster adaptive coping behaviors, such as collaboration and shared planning. Their research supported the idea that peer mentoring and leadership sensitivity greatly reduce teacher stress. Porsch and Whannell concluded that a positive learning culture within schools enables out-of-field teachers to navigate their roles more confidently. Likewise, Haidar and Fang (2019) explored the emotional and psychological pressures faced by

out-of-field teachers, emphasizing that coping strategies must go beyond instructional techniques. They documented how resilience, reflection, and emotional regulation play a major role in helping teachers stay motivated and effective. Their study suggested that the emotional labor involved in out-of-field assignments often leads teachers to adopt mindfulness and reframing techniques. These internal mechanisms are essential for sustaining motivation and job satisfaction under challenging conditions.

3.2.2. *Collaboration and Peer Support*—

Collaboration with colleagues and other professionals serves as a vital mechanism for coping with the demands of out-of-field teaching. Teachers often seek advice, lesson plans, and strategies from peers who are experts in the subject they've been assigned. This support reduces their anxiety and provides them with practical, tried-and-tested teaching tools. Peer learning bridges the gap between inexperience and competence. The presence of a collaborative environment reinforces the idea that teaching is a communal responsibility. Teachers recognize that they do not have to navigate the challenges alone and that reaching out is not a sign of weakness but a sign of professionalism. These collaborations help build confidence, offer emotional reassurance, and foster camaraderie among faculty. The collective effort improves not only individual performance but the overall learning environment in schools. Arendain and Limpot (2022) focused on the Filipino context, identifying that many teachers cope by finding creative ways to balance learning new content with their daily teaching duties. Their phenomenological study showed that teachers often rely on improvisation, trial-and-error, and peer consultation to survive in out-of-field roles. Arendain and Limpot emphasized the importance of school-led seminars and support groups to mitigate stress. They concluded that while coping is highly individualized, structured institutional support signifi-

cantly enhances teacher well-being.

3.2.3. Positive Mindset and Professional Commitment—One of the most powerful coping mechanisms reported is maintaining a positive mindset and strong professional dedication. Teachers emphasized the value of staying motivated, embracing change, and doing their best regardless of the circumstances. This intrinsic motivation enables them to remain resilient and productive, even when overwhelmed. A growth-oriented perspective allows teachers to see challenges as opportunities for self-improvement. Teachers also expressed that passion for teaching plays a critical role in navigating unfamiliar subjects. Their sense of duty to students and love for the profession fuels their perseverance. Even when lacking expertise, many respond with optimism and determination, committed to making the best of the assignment. This psychological strength is often what sustains them during tough transitions and workload pressures. Coping with out-of-field teaching requires a multidimensional approach, combining personal agency with institutional reinforcement. Teachers relied heavily on self-directed learning, collaborative planning with peers, and continuous reflection to manage the instructional and emotional demands of teaching outside their expertise. The presence of supportive school leaders, mentoring opportunities, and relevant training greatly enhanced their ability to thrive despite the challenges. This theme suggests that a strong coping system is not built on individual effort alone, but on a shared responsibility between educators and the institution. Teachers shared that while passion and initiative help them persevere, institutional sup-

port is what sustains long-term success. Some expressed that without mentoring and collaborative learning communities, they would have felt isolated and overwhelmed. They also acknowledged that tailored professional development and accessible resources played a major role in building their competence and confidence. Ultimately, the insights point to a systemic need to formalize support structures, recognizing that teacher well-being directly influences student outcomes and school performance. The insights gained from teachers' lived experiences reflect this dynamic interplay, suggesting that a holistic approach combining environmental adaptation and social constructivist practices is essential for empowering out-of-field educators and enhancing educational outcomes. Teachers emphasized the value of internal motivation, a growth mindset, and a strong sense of purpose in adapting to out-of-field teaching. Their intrinsic drive, rooted in their commitment to students, helped them seek resources and improve their practice despite various pressures. However, they also acknowledged that personal effort alone was not enough, without structured guidance and timely support, their progress was often slow, highlighting the importance of combining self-agency with institutional assistance. In addition, many teachers faced a temporary loss of confidence as their professional identity was challenged by teaching outside their specialization. Over time, with the help of supportive environments, they redefined their roles, shifting from being subject experts to becoming adaptable, reflective educators. This transformation allowed them to rebuild their sense of professional self and embrace change as part of their growth.

3.3. Insights and Lesson Learned Drawn from the Study—The findings highlight how crucial flexibility and a commitment to lifelong learning are for teachers working outside their field of expertise. Participants shared that adapt-

ing to unfamiliar subjects required an open attitude and the drive to continually develop new knowledge and skills. This adaptability helped them become more resilient and allowed them to approach challenges as opportunities for per-

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms on the Challenges of Out-of-Field Teaching

sonal and professional growth. Lifelong learning was seen not just as a requirement but as a meaningful pursuit that enhanced their teaching practice. The responses also revealed the essential role of support systems and institutional development, along with the impact of passion and dedication beyond formal expertise. Participants noted that mentorship, collaboration with colleagues, and targeted professional development offered vital guidance and encouragement. Even when subject mastery was limited, their enthusiasm for teaching and strong sense of responsibility toward students helped them succeed. These lessons suggest that passion, combined with a nurturing environment, is a powerful force in enabling teachers to excel in out-of-field assignments.

3.3.1. Embracing Flexibility and Lifelong Learning —A major insight from teachers engaged in out-of-field assignments is the importance of flexibility and continuous learning. Teachers recognized that adapting to new sub-

jects pushes them to embrace change, go beyond comfort zones, and adopt a growth mindset. This adaptability is seen not just as a survival skill, but as a critical quality that enhances teaching effectiveness in varied and unpredictable environments. Lifelong learning becomes a necessary philosophy, one that enriches both the teacher and the student. These experiences underscore that out-of-field teaching is not merely a professional demand, but it is an opportunity for transformation. Through exposure to new content areas, teachers develop resilience and reinforce the habit of seeking knowledge, which is transferable to any teaching context. In doing so, they model the very values of curiosity, learning, and perseverance that they wish to instill in their learners. The results of the study support Kenny et al. (2020), which noted that one of the key insights gained from out-of-field teaching is the realization that flexibility and continuous learning are essential attributes of modern educators. His research revealed that

teachers often reframe their assignments as opportunities for professional growth rather than obstacles. This mindset leads to improved adaptability, reflective practice, and a stronger connection to lifelong learning. Kenny argued that embracing this perspective transforms professional challenges into meaningful learning experiences. The findings of the study agree with Kenny et al. (2020) highlighted that out-of-field teaching often forces educators to adapt quickly and invest in self-directed professional learning, reflecting the critical need for flexibility in modern teaching environments. Weldon (2019) also emphasized that teachers vary in how they respond to the demands of teaching unfamiliar content, with those who show openness and initiative benefiting the most in terms of professional growth. Du Plessis (2019) pointed out that embracing out-of-field assignments often leads to enriched teaching perspectives, particularly when teachers approach the experience as an opportunity to expand their skills. Napier et al. (2020) further noted that teaching outside one's field often prompts continuous reflection and adjustment, resulting in increased capacity and a deeper commitment to lifelong learning.

3.3.2. Value of Support Systems and Institutional Development—Another key insight centers around the need for strong support systems and institutional strategies to aid out-of-field teachers. Many participants stressed that personal motivation is vital. But systemic support, such as mentoring, relevant training, and accessible resources, is indispensable in improving the experience and effectiveness of teaching out of field. Without this, the quality of teaching and teacher morale can suffer. The findings also suggest that educational institutions must proactively create pathways to support out-of-field teachers through targeted programs and policy adjustments. Training workshops, resource allocation, and peer collaboration opportunities can equip teachers to face these challenges with greater confidence. Teachers also

note the importance of leadership that acknowledges their efforts and aids their development in new subject areas. On the other hand, Du Plessis McDonagh (2021), provided insights into why some teachers hesitate to engage in professional development even when it could aid their performance in out-of-field teaching. They identified a range of factors, including competing demands, lack of time, and fear of being permanently reassigned to the subject. It was concluded that institutional strategies must be both supportive and incentivizing to encourage participation in skill-building activities. These findings underscore the need for well-aligned and empathetic educational policies.

3.3.3. Dedication and Passion Over Expertise—A powerful theme revealed by participants is that effective teaching is not solely based on content expertise but also on passion, commitment, and initiative. Teachers repeatedly stressed that despite being outside their comfort zones, they approached their assignments with seriousness and dedication. This strong sense of professional responsibility often drove them to self-learn, seek help, and perform their roles to the best of their ability. This insight is deeply rooted in the teacher identity that education is a vocation fueled by values more than credentials. Teachers who are driven by passion often bridge the expertise gap through creativity, collaboration, and personal growth. As a result, students still receive meaningful learning experiences even in less-than-ideal teaching assignments. Weldon (2019) emphasized that passion and commitment can often compensate for a lack of content expertise in out-of-field teaching contexts. His study found that dedicated teachers strive to deliver quality instruction regardless of their comfort level with the subject, driven by a deep sense of responsibility to their students. Weldon highlighted that this dedication frequently leads to unexpected professional growth and innovation. These insights reinforce the idea that personal values and intrinsic mo-

Fig. 5. Insights and Lesson Learned Drawn from the Study

tivation are central to effective teaching. The overarching insight is that out-of-field teaching, when supported and reflected upon, can evolve from a deficit model into a growth-oriented opportunity for educators and institutions alike. This growing body of literature, supported by the findings of this study, reinforces the idea that the challenges of out-of-field teaching can be mitigated by shifting the narrative from deficit to development. When schools actively promote a culture of support, learning, and adaptability, teachers are more empowered to approach unfa-

miliar subjects not with fear, but with curiosity and determination. The participants' experiences echo Du Plessis's (2019) assertion that mindset is pivotal, those who perceived out-of-field teaching as a learning journey rather than a professional setback were more likely to thrive. Therefore, reframing out-of-field assignments as professional growth opportunities rather than burdens could inspire policies that prioritize teacher development, continuous learning, and flexible expertise over rigid specialization.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a detailed synthesis of the professional growth experiences of junior high school teachers as they navigate the realities of out-of-field teaching. Grounded in the findings of the study, it highlights the educators' journey of empowerment amid subject-area misalignment, institutional constraints, and evolving classroom demands. The research focused on understanding the strategies these teachers employed to adapt, the challenges they encountered in delivering instruction beyond their areas of specialization, and the transformative insights they gained through the process. Utilizing a qualitative phenomenological design and guided by Creswell's

(2020) framework for thematic analysis, the study relied on open-ended interviews to elicit rich, first-hand narratives that illuminate the complexity and resilience embedded in the lived experiences of out-of-field educators.

4.1. Findings—This study reveals critical implications for multiple layers of the educational system, particularly in relation to teacher assignment practices, professional development, and institutional support. The findings emphasized that out-of-field teaching is not merely a staffing issue but a pedagogical and systemic concern with direct impacts on teacher efficacy and student learning outcomes. Teachers' lived experiences highlight the need for schools and education departments to adopt responsive measures that bridge the gap between teacher specialization and subject area demands. Equally, the ability of teachers to cope, through self-directed learning, peer support, and values-driven commitment, suggests that with proper scaffolding, even non-specialists can develop into competent, adaptive educators. However, such success hinges on the presence of sustained institutional support, appropriate training, and emotionally intelligent leadership. Therefore, the study affirms the urgency of aligning teacher deployment with subject mastery, and concurrently investing in structured capacity-building systems to empower educators assigned to teach outside their field.

4.2. Implications—The study's findings closely tie into the Person-Environment Fit Theory. They show how out-of-field teachers struggle with mismatches between their skills and the demands of the subjects they are required to teach. Many educators expressed feelings of inadequacy and stress when their expertise did not match their teaching responsibilities, indicating a low person-job fit. This mismatch often led to a loss of confidence and job satisfaction as teachers found it hard to meet curricular expectations without adequate preparation or support. However, the study also found that when schools provided focused pro-

fessional development and fostered supportive environments that recognized teachers' individual needs and backgrounds, the fit improved. This better fit resulted in higher motivation, increased classroom effectiveness, and improved overall well-being, confirming that optimizing person-environment compatibility is vital in addressing challenges faced by out-of-field teachers. Vygotsky's Social Constructivist Theory offers another perspective, showing how teachers develop knowledge and skills through social interaction and collaboration. The findings indicate that those who participated in collaborative learning communities, peer mentoring, and professional discussions were better prepared to deal with the complexities of teaching unfamiliar content. These interactions helped build their understanding, lessen feelings of isolation, and develop new teaching skills. Vygotsky's focus on the social and cultural context of learning reinforces the need for collaborative school environments where educators can share expertise, resources, and emotional support, encouraging a shared growth mindset amid out-of-field demands. The integration of both theoretical frameworks, Person-Environment Fit and Social Constructivism, illustrates the dual nature of the out-of-field teaching experience. On one side, it highlights systemic mismatches between teacher capabilities and environmental demands; on the other, it shows how social learning and teamwork can turn these challenges into opportunities for growth. Together, these views stress the importance of evaluating both individual-context alignment and the quality of professional interactions to design effective support strategies for out-of-field teachers. The study also pointed out that adjusting content and teaching methods is one of the biggest challenges for out-of-field educa-

tors. This stresses the need for teacher education institutions and the Department of Education (DepEd) to reevaluate their teacher preparation frameworks. Pre-service training should include exposure to various teaching strategies to better equip future teachers for handling subjects beyond their specialization. For school administrators, this means ensuring access to resources and coaching specific to the subjects taught to support newly reassigned teachers. Despite the difficulties, the emergence of innovative teaching strategies shows teachers' ability to adapt and engage students in new ways. Teachers used their diverse backgrounds to create interdisciplinary lessons that made learning more relevant. These findings suggest that curriculum developers and professional development providers should encourage flexibility and creativity in lesson planning. DepEd should establish platforms for sharing innovations, like Learning Action Cells (LACs) and Professional Learning Communities (PLCs), to help educators exchange adaptable strategies. The theme of emotional pressure and performance anxiety points to the mental costs of out-of-field teaching. Teachers reported increased stress due to unfamiliar content and rising expectations, highlighting the urgent need for psychological and professional support systems. Schools should prioritize wellness programs, accessible mentoring systems, and a kinder approach to teacher evaluations. Policymakers must think about including mental health support and workload-balancing strategies in schools, particularly for those teaching multiple or non-specialized subjects. In response to these challenges, many teachers turned to self-directed learning and personal initiative. They independently explored their new subject areas, attended training, and collaborated with colleagues. This emphasizes the importance of supporting teacher autonomy with flexible, self-paced learning modules, both online and offline, designed for out-of-field contexts. School leaders should also recognize and

back self-initiated efforts by allowing time for independent study and offering learning credits. Collaboration and peer support became vital coping mechanisms for bridging subject-matter gaps and sustaining teacher motivation. The study highlights the need for school administrators to promote cooperative teaching models and structured peer mentoring. DepEd regional and division offices should create learning hubs or support clusters that enable out-of-field teachers to regularly consult with subject experts and exchange strategies. The theme of a positive mindset and professional commitment further underscores how intrinsic motivation helps overcome out-of-field challenges. Teachers who approached their work with openness, resilience, and dedication found it easier to adapt and deliver effective instruction. These findings suggest that teacher preparation programs should include values formation, reflective practice, and resilience-building elements. Additionally, policy changes should reward commitment-driven performance through incentives such as awards, career advancement opportunities, and lighter administrative loads. A broader realization from the study is the importance of flexibility and lifelong learning. Out-of-field teaching encouraged many educators to see teaching as a dynamic practice that extends beyond subject expertise. This insight has implications for educational planning and policy, urging stakeholders to incorporate lifelong learning into career progression frameworks. For teachers, it emphasizes the need to maintain a growth mindset and be open to interdisciplinary roles across different grade levels. The study also stressed the importance of support systems and institutional development in shaping teacher performance. Teachers thrived when schools offered consistent mentoring, relevant training, and timely access to teaching materials. This suggests that DepEd should build strong support systems into performance evaluations, and not just focusing on outcomes but also assessing the institu-

tional conditions that influence teacher success. Strengthening these systems will lead to fairer and more sustainable teaching environments. Finally, the theme of dedication and passion over expertise highlights the human side of effective teaching. While content knowledge matters, participants noted that passion, adaptability, and a strong sense of purpose often made the biggest difference in student engagement and success. Therefore, recruitment and evaluation processes should balance academic qualifications with soft skills like commitment, empathy, and resilience. Policymakers must create more holistic models of teacher performance that recognize both expertise and a genuine dedication to teaching, particularly in out-of-field contexts.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study’s findings, it is essential that the results are effectively communicated and utilized by the significant individuals for whom this research was designed. Teachers

Teachers might be provided with access to continuous professional learning, including subject-specific training, mentoring, and collaboration opportunities. Future directions encourage the creation of teacher learning communities (TLCs) where educators, especially those teaching out-of-field can co-plan, co-teach, and reflect together. Teachers are also encouraged to maintain reflective practice and take ownership of their professional growth by embracing lifelong learning as a central principle in their career journey.

Learners

The study suggests the need for a more student-centered perspective in assigning teachers to specific subjects. Learners benefit most when teachers are confident and competent in their subject areas. Thus, it is important for schools to create feedback mechanisms that allow students to express their experiences with out-of-field teachers.

School Administrators

Principals and department heads play a piv-

otal role in either mitigating or exacerbating the challenges of out-of-field teaching. Future initiatives should empower school leaders to perform regular needs assessments, implement mentoring systems, and advocate for strategic teacher placement. Administrators must also foster a supportive culture where teachers feel psychologically safe to seek help and share their struggles, thereby enhancing job satisfaction and instructional performance.

DepEd Officials

At the division and regional levels, DepEd officials might institutionalize responsive programs tailored to address out-of-field teaching realities. This includes investing in subject-matter upskilling programs, allocating budget for teacher development, and ensuring the equitable deployment of teachers based on specialization and school needs. Policies could be data-driven, informed by grassroots realities, and designed to promote teacher well-being, not just compliance with staffing quotas.

Policymakers

Legislators and national education authorities might consider enacting policies that minimize out-of-field teaching by addressing root causes such as teacher shortages, lack of subject specialization, and resource inequity. Future policy directions should include provisions for teacher incentives, load reduction for out-of-field teachers, and mandatory training for those reassigned to new subjects. It is also essential to legislate stronger teacher recruitment frameworks aligned with curriculum demands, particularly in underserved and rural areas.

Future Researchers

Future studies may explore the longitudinal effects of out-of-field teaching on teacher retention, learner outcomes, and school performance. Comparative studies across regions or school types (urban vs. rural) could yield insights into context-specific challenges and effective practices. Researchers are also encouraged to investigate the psychological impacts of out-of-field

assignments and the effectiveness of various intervention models, such as peer mentoring and subject-specific crash courses. Additionally, studies incorporating learner perspectives can further enrich the discourse on instructional quality and teacher impact. Expanding on these directions, future research could also examine how institutional culture and leadership styles influence the experiences of out-of-field teachers over time. Investigating how different administrative approaches, such as collaborative planning, distributed leadership, and recognition practices. These affect teacher motivation and adaptability could offer valuable insights for policy and practice. Moreover, exploring the role of technology in supporting out-of-field teaching, particularly in remote areas, may reveal scalable solutions that enhance both teacher preparedness and student engagement.

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